

**Sterols and Terpenes of the Marine Green
Algal Species *Caulerpa racemosa* and
*Codium decorticatum***

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WE have recently reported the presence of some new aromatic compounds¹ from the chloroform extract and a new sesquiterpene in addition to two new red caulerpin analogues² from the ethyl acetate extract of the green algal species, *Caulerpa racemosa* collected off Visakhapatnam coast. We, now report the isolation of β -sitosterol, caulerpin, the red pigment, *trans*- and *cis*-phytols from its hexane extract. This is the first report of the presence of *cis*- and *trans*-phytols from any caulerpa species.

We also report here in the chemical examination of another green algal species, *Codium decorticatum* collected from Mandapam coast. Two sterols have been separated from its ethyl acetate extract and they were identified as aplysterol and 24,28-didehydroaplysterol. The compounds were characterised by chemical and spectroscopic data and by comparison with authentic samples wherever possible.

C. racemosa: The residue (5 g) obtained by the evaporation of the hexane extract of the dry powder

of *C. racemosa* (3 kg) was chromatographed over a column of silica gel (100–200 mesh) to yield four compounds: β -sitosterol (hexane-benzene, 4:6; 25 mg), colourless needles, m.p. 136–38°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -36^\circ$; caulerpin (benzene; 100 mg), orange red prisms, m.p. 316–18°, $C_{24}H_{38}O_4N_2$ (lit.^{3,4} m.p. 317°); *trans*-phytol (benzene-ethyl acetate, 19:1), colourless oil, $C_{20}H_{40}O$; λ_{max} (MeOH) no absorption above 210 nm; ν_{max} (neat) 3400br, 2950, 1650, 1450 and 1010 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.90 (12H, d, J 6 Hz), 1.2–1.6 (20H, m), 1.65 (3H, s), 1.95 (2H, m), 4.05 (2H, d, J 6.4 Hz) and 5.3 (1H, t, J 6.4 Hz); m/z M^+ (296) and it was identified as *trans*-phytol⁵; *cis*-phytol (benzene: ethyl acetate 19:1), colourless oil, $C_{20}H_{40}O$; λ_{max} (MeOH) no absorption above 210 nm; ν_{max} (neat) 3400br, 2950, 1650, 1450 and 1010 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$): 0.90 (12H, d, J 6 Hz), 1.2–1.6 (20H, m), 1.7 (3H, s), 2.0 (2H, m), 4.4 (2H, d, J 6.4 Hz) and 5.33 (1H, t, J 6.4 Hz); m/z M^+ (269) and it was identified as *cis*-phytol⁵.

C. decorticatum: The dry powder (500 g) of *C. decorticatum* was extracted with ethyl acetate. The residue (1.5 g) obtained by the evaporation of the ethyl acetate extract on chromatography over a column of silica gel (100–200 mesh) yielded two crystalline compounds: aplysterol (24,26-dimethylcholest-5-ene-3 β -ol⁶; 10 mg), colourless prisms, m.p. 132–34° (lit.⁶ 135–36°), $C_{29}H_{50}O$; $[\alpha]_D^{25} -25^\circ$; λ_{max} ($CHCl_3$) no absorption above 210 nm; ν_{max} ($CHCl_3$) 3400br, 2950, 1450 and 1040 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.70 (3H, s, 18- CH_3), 1.00 (3H, s, 19- CH_3), 3.40 (1H, m, $CHOH$) and 5.30 (1H, m, $CH=C$); m/z M^+ (414); 24,28-didehydroaplysterol (26-methyl-24-methylenecholest-5-ene-3 β -ol⁶; 10 mg), colourless prisms, m.p. 126–28° (lit.⁶ 128–30°), $C_{29}H_{50}O$; $[\alpha]_D^{25} -37^\circ$; λ_{max} ($CHCl_3$) no absorption above 210 nm; ν_{max} ($CHCl_3$) 3400br, 2950, 1450, 1040 and 885 cm^{-1} ; δ ($CDCl_3$) 0.70 (3H, s, 18- CH_3), 1.0 (3H, s, 19- CH_3), 3.4 (1H, m, $-CHOH$), 4.68 (2H, s, $=CH_2$) and 5.3 (1H, m, $CH=C$); m/z M^+ (412).

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